

Up to 1 g CO₂eq is released per minute when using social media [1].

Social media networks vary a lot, TikTok und YouTube for example, release twice as much CO₂eq per minute as Twitch and X (Twitter) [1].

Streaming using Mobile-data releases 7 times (5G) to 180 times (3G) more CO₂eq compared to fiber optics [2-4].

High-quality audio streaming consumes approximately 72 MB per hour and releases around 4.2 g CO₂eq [4-6].

Video-Streaming on smartphones in Germany releases an average of around 54 g CO₂eq per hour [4,6].

Mobile-Gaming releases around 7 g CO₂eq per hour [6, 7].

The use of cloud storage releases around 130 g CO₂eq per GB per year [2].

Sending an email or text message releases around 0.2 g CO₂eq [8,9].

A single search query releases around 0.12 g CO₂eq [10-12].

Each request to a generative AI generates approximately 4.3 g CO₂eq [11-14].

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